

Open Science – Concepts and Practices

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7428843>

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/97/The_Earth_seen_from_Apollo_17.jpg

Cost per Genome

A close-up photograph of two cats huddled together on a grey, textured blanket. The cats have brown and white fur. One cat is in the foreground, and the other is slightly behind it. A semi-transparent white rectangular box is overlaid in the center of the image, containing the text "Open & FAIR".

Open & FAIR

Key message:

Openness, transparency, reproducibility are core values of science.

Natural Sciences

Open Science

Making science more accessible, inclusive and equitable for the benefit of all

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

In a world first, UNESCO sets international standards for open science

Discover

<https://www.unesco.org/en/natural-sciences/open-science>

Global call for best practices in open science

Contribute

Call for papers The deadline is extended until 24 July 2022

Open science policies as an accelerator for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals

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1. Incentives & Culture
 2. Infrastructure
 3. Awareness/Knowledge/Skills

1. Incentives & Culture

LEIDEN MANIFESTO FOR RESEARCH METRICS

Résumé for Researchers

Opening up conversations about researcher evaluation

Résumé for Researchers has been created to support the evaluation of individuals' varied contributions to research. Find out more about the background to the tool [in our blog](#).

Sustained excellence in research requires a range of contributions

By creating a working environment that is both challenging and supportive, researchers help improve the flow of ideas, encourage talent to join their organisations and nurture future generations of researchers. To make the decisions concerning the people that create such an environment, decision-makers need to be able to assess the previous contributions made by individuals.

Over the years, the research community has developed ways of assessing contributions to the development of new ideas often by focusing on individuals' portfolios of outputs and the impact of their work. However, a researcher's overall contribution to research goes beyond their easily attributable outputs and impact. Too narrowly focused performance indicators can make it harder to see, reward or nurture the full range of contributions that are necessary to create the environments that enable excellence and steward it for the future. To recognise these wider contributions, the Society aims to prompt conversations on the evaluation of researchers.

Showing the full range of an individual's contributions to excellent research

To prompt such conversations the Society has developed Résumé for Researchers, which is intended to help researchers to share their varied contributions to research in a consistent way and across a wide range of circumstances.

Résumé for Researchers is not designed to replace more granular information where needed. The strength of the tool lies in its ability to provide a concise overview of an individual. It draws from other established and internationally recognised biosketches, assessment matrices and application forms, as well as having the Society's own evaluation methodology at its heart.

<https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/projects/research-culture/tools-for-support/resume-for-researchers/>

Downloads

[Résumé for Researchers suggested template](#)

PDF, 114.5KB

[← Tools to support and steward research culture](#)

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Scientific Communication and

2. Infrastructure

re3data.org

REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

Search

Text/Manuscript

Code/Models

Data

3. Awareness/Knowledge/Skills

MIND THE GAP

Key message:

To open up science further we need better incentives, solid infrastructure and training to equip more people with necessary skills.

A top-down view of a buffet table. The top half features several white square trays containing fresh green leafy salads, including spinach, arugula, and mixed greens. Below these are trays of sliced tomatoes, sliced cucumbers, and other vegetables. The bottom half of the image shows a large black tray divided into several sections, each containing a different food item: green beans, yellow corn, red kidney beans, sliced red bell peppers, green peas, shredded yellow cheese, cubed white cheese, and sliced pink ham. Two whole tomatoes are placed on the black tray as garnishes. A semi-transparent grey box with white text is centered over the middle of the image.

”Open Science is like a buffet:
take what you can and what benefits you now
– come back for more!”

Data literacy is the ability to collect, manage, evaluate, and apply data, in a critical manner.

**THE
CARPENTRIES**

**We teach foundational coding and
data science skills to researchers
worldwide.**

PUSH TO
RESET THE
WORLD

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- A close-up photograph of a blue-painted metal surface, possibly a door or a cabinet. The paint is chipped and peeling in several places, revealing a rusty, brown metal underneath. A brass padlock is attached to the surface, and a keyhole is visible. The padlock has the word "STERLING" and a logo of a bird with spread wings embossed on it. A key is inserted into the keyhole. The background is a solid blue color with some white speckles.
- Openness, transparency, reproducibility are core values of science.
 - To open up science further we need better incentives, solid infrastructure and training to equip more people with necessary skills.
 - You and your organisation can help driving this change.

<http://www.opensciencerradio.org/>

Thank you for your attention.

What are your questions?

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